

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15021829

Prevalence and Risk Factors of Hepatitis Virus Infections among Pregnant Women Attending Primary Healthcare Facility in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the prevalence and risk factors of hepatitis virus infections among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. A hospital based descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted for the study. A 5years retrospective study (January 2018 to August, 2022) of diagnosed case of hepatitis B infection managed at the primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was conducted. The population for this study consisted of 10874 registered pregnant women from the primary health care facility as at time of the study from January 2018 to August 2022 in selected health facility in Port Harcourt city and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size for this study was 500 (n=500) which was determined using Taro Yamene formula. Taro Yamene Formula was used to obtain the sample size with 95% confidence level. A multi stage sampling procedure was adopted for the study which was done in three stages. The instrument for data collection was self-structured proforma designed by the researcher titled: Prevalence and Risk Factors of Hepatitis B Infection among Pregnant Women (PRFHBIPW). Proforma does not undergo reliability test but was checked on whether it can obtain information recorded on the patient's folder or case note for a specific duration. Data collected for this study was analyzed using Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS) version 25.0. The result indicated that less than three quarter (20.3%) of the women were diagnosed with HepB virus while 79.7% did not have the virus. The result showed that those who had family history of Hepatitis B were 3.92 times more likely to have HBV (OR= 3.92, 95%CI: 3.05 – 5.04) compared to those who had no family history HBV. The result showed that those who had

multiple sexual partner were 3.93 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.93, 95%CI: 3.09 – 4.99) compared to those who had no multiple sexual partner. The result showed that those who had history of blood transfusion were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.01 – 5.08) compared to those who had no history of blood transfusion. The result showed that those who had previous abortion were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.00 – 5.10) compared to those who had no previous abortion. The result showed that those who had previous STIs were 3.92 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.00 – 5.10) compared to those who had no previous STIs. It was concluded that the prevalence of hepatitis B infection was low but the prevalence rate differs in associated factors such as family history, unscreened blood transfusion, multiple sexual partner, previous abortion and reported cases of sexually transmitted infections. It was recommended that government should make nationwide policy of routine and widespread HBV screening and prevention though vaccination among pregnant women in order to improve maternal and child health.

Keywords: hepatitis B infection, blood transfusion, pregnant women, primary healthcare facility

INTRODUCTION

Women of childbearing age are always sexually active and are exposed to multiple sexual partners which create the likelihood of contracting infectious such as hepatitis B virus. Hepatitis virus infection is communicable disease that can spread from one infected person to another especially among pregnant. World Health Organization (2022) estimated that 296 million people were living with chronic hepatitis B infection in 2019, with 1.5 million new infections each year. In 2019, hepatitis B resulted in an estimated 820 000 deaths, mostly from cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (primary liver cancer). Hepatitis B is a potentially life-threatening liver infection caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV). It is a major global health problem. It can cause chronic infection and puts people at high risk of death from cirrhosis and liver cancer. A safe and effective vaccine that offers 98% to 100% protection against hepatitis B is available (World Health Organization 2020). Preventing hepatitis B infection averts the development of complications including chronic disease and liver cancer. The burden of hepatitis B infection is highest in the WHO Western Pacific Region and the WHO African Region, where 116 million and 81 million people, respectively, are chronically infected. Sixty million people are infected in the World Health Organization Eastern Mediterranean Region, 18 million in the World Health Organization South-East Asia Region, 14 million in the World Health Organization European Region and 5 million in the WHO Region of the Americas (WHO, 2022). World Health Organization (2022) estimated that 296 million people were living with chronic hepatitis B infection in 2019, with 1.5 million new infections each year. In 2019, hepatitis B resulted in an estimated 820 000 deaths, mostly from cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (primary liver cancer). Hepatitis B infection acquired in adulthood leads to chronic hepatitis in less than 5% of cases, whereas infection in infancy and early childhood leads to chronic hepatitis in about 95% of cases (WHO 2022). This is the basis for strengthening and prioritizing infant and childhood vaccination. The hepatitis B virus can survive outside the body for at least 7 days.

The prevalence of hepatitis virus infection is increasing as it affects pregnant women. Polaris Observatory Collaborators, (2018) reported that around 1.8 (1.6-2.2) million infections were in children aged 5 years, with a prevalence of 1.4% (1.2-1.6) while an estimated that 87% of infants had received the three-dose HBV vaccination in the first year of life, 46% had received timely birth-dose vaccination, and 13% had received hepatitis B immunoglobulin along with the full vaccination regimen. Kiefe, et al (2021) reported that the overall prevalence of hepatitis virus infection was 9.2% of pregnant women while 46.7% prevalence rate was found among pregnant women aged 25 to 34 years. Bancha et al. (2020) added that prevalence of Hepatitis B surface antigen among pregnant women was 49(7.3%) while pregnant women with history of multiple sexual partners and surgical procedure were 2.6 times and 3.2 times more likely to contract hepatitis virus infection. Shedain, et al. (2017) revealed that prevalence of hepatitis infections was 17 times high among pregnant women and 48 times higher in HIV positive pregnant women. Studies in Nigeria by Musa, et al, (2015) indicated that 14% of pregnant women screen of hepatitis virus infection were positive especially among those who attending antenatal clinic. Yazie, and Tebeje (2019) affirmed

that large proportion (6%) of pregnant women booked were diagnosed hepatitis virus infection. Ekouevi et al. (2020) illustrated about 35% of women were screened for HBV during antenatal care and 85% of infants received three doses of HBV immunization and among mothers, the prevalence of HBV was 10.6% and 177 had detectable HBV viral load (> 10 IU/mL). Additionally, Fomulu et al. (2013) illustrated that prevalence of hepatitis B infection (HBsAg) among antenatal clinic attendants in our setting was 7.7% rate of HBV infectivity was high, with 28% of HBsAg positive women having evidence of HBeAg in their plasma, and up to 45.8% of these women lacking antibodies against hepatitis B e antigen (anti-HBe) while 41% of the pregnant women had had previous contact with HBV as evidenced by the positive status for anti-HBc. Just 2.7% of the pregnant women had previously been vaccinated against HBV. Previous case of sexually transmitted infections could be another risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women of childbearing age. Hepatitis B infection is a viral infection that could be transferrable from infected person to non-infected women. Women who are sexually active might some unprotected intercourse which may be traceable contraction of infectious such as hepatitis B infection. Kinfe, et al (2021) revealed that women who had reported cases of sexually transmitted infections are more likely contract hepatitis B as one of the STIs. Demeke, et al (2021) reported that history of hepatitis B and other STIs in the family are over 7 times more likely to be significantly associated with hepatitis B infections among women. Banacha, et al, (2020) illustrated that the prevalence of hepatitis B infection is more higher among women with reported cases of sexually transmitted infections resulting from unprotected sexually intercourse with infected partners. Ekouevi et al. (2020) in their study that the prevalence rate of 10.6 at 95% confidence interval is increasing as case of other STIs are reported. Sibia et al. (2016) put up that reported case of HBV co-infections are more likely to correlate with hepatitis B infection among pregnant women. Multiple sexual partner among women of childbearing especially among pregnant women would be likely to contract hepatitis B infections. Pregnant women with history of multiple sexual partners would be at risk of infectious diseases especially hepatitis B infections. Talla, et al (2022) illustrated that women with multiple sexual partners are over 2 times more likely to be diagnosed of hepatitis B infections and other STIs. Demeke, et al (2021) that multiple sexual partners showed over 4 times a significant risk factor of hepatitis B infection and other infectious diseases. Gedefaw, et al (2019) buttressed that women having a history of multiple sexual partners were over 4 times to reported magnitude of hepatitis B infections. Adegbesan-Omilabu, et al (2015) revealed that women with two or more lifetime sexual partners were 4 times more likely to reported cases of hepatitis B infections. It is plausible that most young women might have several sexual partners would have unprotected sexual intercourse are at risk of infectious disease such as hepatitis B among others. Unscreened blood transfusion has been a means of transmitting several infections that threatened health of the population including pregnant women. Women who had received blood that is unscreened might end up having infectious disease like hepatitis B infections. Evidently, Demeke, et al (2021) in their study revealed that unscreened blood transfused in to a sick person have been more risky and serve a vehicle of disease transmission such as HIV, hepatitis B and other infections. Additionally, Israr, et al (2021) illustrated that blood transfusion ($P = 0.0005$) were significantly allied with HBV infection while surgical procedure ($P = 0.0001$) was significantly associated with HCV infection. Mac, et al (2019) reported that good proportion of hepatitis B positive cases are traceable of reception of unscreened blood transfusion than any other source. In a study of Gedefaw, et al (2019) that having history of blood transfusion, was 5 times significantly associated risk factor with Hepatitis B viral infection. Dongdem, et al, (2012) added that unscreened blood donors contribute to the transmission of infectious disease and health disorders. It is possible that infected person might be a voluntary blood donor and if not properly screened the distribution of infectious diseases might be contracted by those who need blood transfusion. Dongdem et al. (2012) reported that group of voluntary blood donors are 4 times more likely to to be HBsAg especially with the age of 20-29 years. Consequent upon this underlining problem, the study seeks to investigate the prevalence and risk factors of hepatitis virus infections among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence and risk factors of hepatitis virus infections among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Early sexual debut is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis;
2. Family history is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis virus infection among women attending antenatal clinic.
3. Multiple sexual partner is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis;
4. History of blood transfusion is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis;
5. Previous STIs is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis;

Methodology

Study setting: The area of the study was Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State, Nigeria. The modern health care centres (MHCs) established in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt city that carried out maternal service such as antenatal service at the primary level of health delivery.

Study Design: A hospital based descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted for the study. A 5years retrospective study (January 2018 to August, 2022) of diagnosed case of hepatitis B infection managed at the primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was conducted. Cases were identified using the diagnostic medical registration record.

Population for the Study: The population for this study consisted of 10874 registered pregnant women from the primary health care facility as at time of the study from January 2018 to August 2022 in selected health facility in Port Harcourt city and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State (Source: Medical Record Departments, 2022).

Sample and Sampling Technique: The sample size for this study was 500 (n=500) which was determined using Taro Yamene formula. Taro Yamene Formula was used to obtain the sample size with 95% confidence level.

Taro Yamene formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Added 25% of non-response was added

$$n = 100 + 400 \text{ given } 500 \text{ (sample size)}$$

However, the sample size was increased by 100 to give the sample size of 500 to represent the population.

A multi stage sampling procedure was adopted for the study which was done in three stages include:

Stage one: simple random sampling technique was employed to select Port Harcourt city and Obio/Akpor Local Government area metropolis which comprised of the municipals from the four of Rivers State by balloting without replacement. Stage two: Simple random sampling technique was used select twelve (12) model primary health care centres in Port Harcourt city and Obio/Akpor Local Government area which include model primary health care centre (MPHCC) Rumueme, Rummodamaya, Rumuigbo, Ozuoba, Eneka, Rumukurushi, Orogbom, Churchill, Borokiri, Azuabie, Amadi-Ama and Pott Johnson comprehensive health centre balloting without replacement. This is done to enable the researcher have access to the data from the sample (patient’s folder) in different health care centers for the study. Stage three: Stratified non-proportionate sampling technique was used select 42 pregnant women attending antenatal clinic from both selected primary health care facilities to make up the sample.

Instrumentation: The instrument for data collection was self-structured proforma designed by the researcher titled: Prevalence and Risk Factors of Hepatitis B Infection among Pregnant Women

(PRFHBIPW). The proforma was design to collect data from the patient’s folder case note in the primary health care centres on the prevalence and risk factors of hepatitis B.

Validity of the Instrument: The Proforma was validated by the researcher’s supervisor and three other experts in department of Human Kinetic, Health and Safety Studies. To establish its content validity. Suggestions from these lecturers were incorporated in designing the final copy of the proforma. Hence the proforma was valid and was used for the study.

Method of Data Analysis: Data collected for this study was analyzed using Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS) version 25.0. Inferential statistical tool such as multiple (binary) regression model was used test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Analysis based on 439 from 500 instruments was used for the study given 87.8% return rate upon which data analysis was done.

What is the prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis?

Table 1.1: Frequency distribution showing the prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Diagnosis of HBV	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
Yes	89	20.3	Low prevalence
No	350	79.7	
Total	439	100.0	

Table 1.1 revealed the prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis. The result indicated that less than three quarter (20.3%) of the women were diagnosed with HepB virus while 79.7% did not have the virus. Thus, the prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was low.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Family history is not significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Table 1.2: Binary logistic regression showing relationship between family history and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Family history	Diagnosis of HBV		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95%CI	
	Yes F(%)	No F(%)						Lower	Upper
No	77(20.3)	302(79.7)	379(100)	1	142.79	0.00*	Ref		
Yes	12(20.0)	48(80.0)	60(100)				3.92	3.05	– 5.04

***Significant. p<0.05**

Table 1.2 showed the binary logistic regression of relationship family history and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women. On bivariate analysis, the findings of the study showed a significant relationship between family history and hepatitis B virus infection (p<0.05). The result showed that those who had family history of Hepatitis B were 3.92 times more likely to have HBV (OR= 3.92, 95%CI: 3.05 – 5.04) compared to those who had no family history HBV. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that family history is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was rejected.

H₀₂: Multiple sexual partner is not significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Table 1.3: Binary logistic regression showing relationship between multiple sexual partner and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Multiple sexual partner	Diagnosis of HBV		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95%CI	
	Yes F(%)	No F(%)						Lower	Upper
No	83(20.3)	326(79.7)	409(100)	1	154.36	0.00*	Ref		
Yes	6(20.0)	24(80.0)	30(100)				3.93	3.09 – 4.99	

***Significant. p<0.05**

Table 1.3 showed the binary logistic regression of relationship multiple sexual partner and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women. On bivariate analysis, the findings of the study showed a significant relationship between multiple sexual partner and hepatitis B virus infection ($p<0.05$). The result showed that those who had multiple sexual partner were 3.93 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.93, 95%CI: 3.09 – 4.99) compared to those who had no multiple sexual partner. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that multiple sexual partner is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was rejected.

H₀₃: History of blood transfusion is not significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Table 1.4: Binary logistic regression showing relationship between history of blood transfusion and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

History of blood transfusion	Diagnosis of HBV		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95%CI	
	Yes F(%)	No F(%)						Lower	Upper
No	71(20.3)	278(79.7)	349(100)	1	131.23	0.00*	Ref		
Yes	18(20.0)	72(80.0)	90(100)				3.91	3.01 – 5.08	

***Significant. p<0.05**

Table 1.4 showed the binary logistic regression of relationship history of blood transfusion and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women. On bivariate analysis, the findings of the study showed a significant relationship between history of blood transfusion and hepatitis B virus infection ($p<0.05$). The result showed that those who had history of blood transfusion were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.01 – 5.08) compared to those who had no history of blood transfusion. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that history of blood transfusion is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was rejected.

H₀₄: Previous abortion is not significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Table 1.5: Binary logistic regression showing relationship between previous abortion and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

History of blood transfusion	Diagnosis of HBV		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95%CI	
	Yes F(%)	No F(%)						Lower	Upper
No	69(20.3)	270(79.7)	339(100)	1	127.38	0.00*	Ref		
Yes	20(20.0)	80(80.0)	100(100)				3.91	3.00 – 5.10	

***Significant. p<0.05**

Table 1.5 showed the binary logistic regression of relationship previous abortion and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women. On bivariate analysis, the findings of the study showed a significant

relationship between previous abortion and hepatitis B virus infection ($p < 0.05$). The result showed that those who had previous abortion were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.00 – 5.10) compared to those who had no previous abortion. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that previous abortion is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was rejected.

H₀₅: Previous STIs is not significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

Table 1.6: Binary logistic regression showing relationship between previous STIs and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis

History of blood transfusion	Diagnosis of HBV		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95%CI	
	Yes F(%)	No F(%)						Lower	Upper
No	71(20.3)	278(79.7)	349(100)	1	131.23	0.00*	Ref		
Yes	18(20.0)	72(80.0)	90(100)				3.92	3.02 – 5.08	

***Significant. $p < 0.05$**

Table 1.6: showed the binary logistic regression of relationship previous STIs and hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women. On bivariate analysis, the findings of the study showed a significant relationship between previous STIs and hepatitis B virus infection ($p < 0.05$). The result showed that those who had previous STIs were 3.92 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.00 – 5.10) compared to those who had no previous STIs. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that previous STIs is not a significant risk factor of hepatitis B virus infection among women attending primary healthcare facility in Port Harcourt metropolis was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of this study showed that those who had family history of Hepatitis B were 3.92 times more likely to have HBV (OR= 3.92, 95%CI: 3.05 – 5.04) compared to those who had no family history HBV. The result of this study is expected because pregnant women who have reported case of hepatitis B in the family might have been exposed to the infection from family members. The result of this study is in credence with studies of Kinfu et al. (2021) reported that the overall prevalence of hepatitis virus infection was 9.2% of pregnant women while 46.7% prevalence rate was found among pregnant women aged 25 to 34 years. Banacha et al. (2020) added that prevalence of Hepatitis B surface antigen among pregnant women was 49(7.3%) while pregnant women with history of multiple sexual partners and surgical procedure were 2.6 times and 3.2 times more likely to contract hepatitis virus infection. Shedain et al. (2017) revealed that prevalence of hepatitis infections was 17 times high among pregnant women and 48 times higher in HIV positive pregnant women. Studies in Nigeria by Musa, et al, (2015) indicated that 14% of pregnant women screen of hepatitis virus infection were positive especially among those who attending antenatal clinic. Yazie and Tebeje (2019) affirmed that large proportion (6%) of pregnant women booked were diagnosed hepatitis virus infection. Ekouevi et al. (2020) illustrated about 35% of women were screened for HBV during antenatal care and 85% of infants received three doses of HBV immunization and among mothers, the prevalence of HBV was 10.6% and 177 had detectable HBV viral load (> 10 IU/mL). The result of this study is in keeping with Fomulu et al. (2013) which illustrated that the prevalence of hepatitis B infection (HBsAg) among pregnant women was 7.7% rate of HBV infectivity was high, with 28% of HBsAg positive women having evidence of HBeAg in their plasma, and up to 45.8% of these women lacking antibodies against hepatitis B e antigen (anti-HBe) while 41% of the pregnant women had had previous contact with HBV as evidenced by the positive status for anti-HBc. Anaedobe et al. (2015) added that the number of positive cases of hepatitis B among pregnant women was 26.7%. It plausible because preventive measures of hepatitis B through vaccination have yield positive result and level of awareness about sexually transmitted infections increasing among populace. Hence, there was low prevalence if hepatitis B infection among pregnant women.

The result showed that those who had multiple sexual partner were 3.93 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.93, 95%CI: 3.09 – 4.99) compared to those who had no multiple sexual partner. The result of this study is required because pregnant women who had multiple sexual partners may have unprotected sexual intercourse with infected person which would the increase the risk of hepatitis B infection. The result of this study is in consonance with Talla et al. (2022) which illustrated that women with multiple sexual partners are over 2 times more likely to be diagnosed of hepatitis B infections and other STIs. Demeke et al. (2021) affirmed that multiple sexual partners showed over 4 times a significant risk factor of hepatitis B infection and other infectious diseases. Gedefaw et al. (2019) buttressed that pregnant women who had history of multiple sexual partners were over 4 times more likelihood of contracting hepatitis B infections. Adegbesan-Omilabu et al. (2015) added that women with two or more lifetime sexual partners were 4 times more likely to reported cases of hepatitis B infections. It is plausible that most young women might have several sexual partners would have unprotected sexual intercourse are at risk of infectious disease such as hepatitis B among others. Anaedobe et al. (2015) concord that women with multiple sexual partners might be about 4 times more significantly associated with prevalence of hepatitis B infections. It is plausible because having sexual partners can expose the person to danger like contracting infectious diseases. It is possible that not all sexual debut can be protected and not all partner can be uninfected. There was no contradictory studies that were found against this study especially as of the time of this present study. Hence, multiple sexual partners constitute a risk factor of hepatitis B infection among pregnant women.

The result showed that those who had history of blood transfusion were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.01 – 5.08) compared to those who had no history of blood transfusion. The result of this study is possible because those who do not confirm whether blood transfuse was screened or not might be at higher risk of contracting infectious diseases such as hepatitis B infection. The result of this study is in agreement with Demeke et al. (2021) which depicted that unscreened blood transfused in to a sick person have been more risky and serve a vehicle of disease transmission such as HIV, hepatitis B and other infections. Israr, et al (2021) buttressed that blood transfusion (P = 0.0005) was significantly allied with Hepatitis B infection especially among pregnant women with shortage of blood that require transfusion. Mac, et al (2019) affirmed that good proportion of hepatitis B positive cases are traceable of reception of unscreened blood transfusion than any other source. In a study of Gedefaw et al. (2019) which agreed that having history of blood transfusion, was 5 times significantly associated risk factor with Hepatitis B viral infection. Dongdem et al. (2012) added that unscreened blood donors contribute to the transmission of infectious disease and health disorders. It is possible that infected person might be a voluntary blood donor and if not properly screened the distribution of infectious diseases might be contracted by those who need blood transfusion. Dongdem et al. (2012) reported that group of voluntary blood donors are 4 times more likely to to be HBsAg especially with the age of 20-29 years. It is plausible because Women who did not confirm screened blood before reception might end up having infectious disease like hepatitis B infections. There was contrary studies that were found against the outcome of this present study. Hence, blood transfusion constitute risk factor of hepatitis B infection

The result showed that those who had previous abortion were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.00 – 5.10) compared to those who had no previous abortion. The result of this study is expected because the tendency if having unsafe abortion is possible which might done with use of unsterilized equipment that would serve as a vehicle of transmitting infectious diseases including hepatitis B infection. The result of this study is in keepings with Talla et al. (2022) and Yazie, and Tebeje (2019) whose studies revealed that unsafe abortion were over 2 times more likely to predict infectious diseases such as hepatitis B. Bigna et al. (2017) illustrated that the risk of hepatitis B infection was significantly high among women with reported cases of unsafe abortion thereby pooled a prevalence rate of 10.6%. Fomulu et al. (2013) added that women who have several cases of abortion were 4 times more likely to be at risk of infectious diseases such as hepatitis B infection. Yong-Ping et al. (2014) affirmed that unsafe abortion have contributed to the prevalence of communicable diseases such as hepatitis B among women of reproductive age. It is plausible because previous experience of abortion may be unsafe which

contribute to the contraction of infectious disease such as hepatitis B. as of the time of this study, there was no prior studies that contradict with the findings of the present study. Hence, previous abortion constitute a predictor of hepatitis B among pregnant women.

The result showed that those who had previous STIs were 3.91 times more likely to be infected with HBV (OR= 3.91, 95%CI: 3.00 – 5.10) compared to those who had no previous STIs. The result of this study is expected because pregnant women with who had suffered for sexually transmitted infections such as hepatitis B may have recurrent case of the infection. The result of this study is in consonance with Kinfe et al. (2021) which revealed that women who had reported cases of sexually transmitted infections are more likely contract hepatitis B as one of the STIs. Demeke et al. (2021) buttressed that previous diagnosis of hepatitis B and other STIs are over 7 times more likely to be significantly associated with hepatitis B infections among women. Bancha, et al. (2020) affirmed that the prevalence of hepatitis B infection is more higher among pregnant women with reported cases of sexually transmitted infections resulting from unprotected sexually intercourse with infected partners. Ekouevi et al. (2020) in their study that the prevalence rate of 10.6 at 95% confidence interval is increasing as case of other STIs were reported among pregnant women. Sibia et al. (2016) agreed that reported case of HBV co-infections are more likely to correlate with hepatitis B infection among pregnant women. Alrowaily et al. (2008) previously added that women of childbearing age with previous cases of syphilis and gonorrhoea are more likely to be diagnosed of hepatitis B infections. It is undeniable because Hepatitis B infection is an infectious disease that can be transferred from infected person to non-infected women. Women who are sexually active might some unprotected sexual intercourse without protective device which put them at risk of contraction of infectious such as hepatitis B infection. However, as of time of this study there was no prior studies that were in contrary with findings of the present study. Hence, previous STIs was significantly associated with the prevalence if hepatitis B infection.

CONCLUSION

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that the prevalence of hepatitis B infection was low but the prevalence rate differs in associated factors such as family history, unscreened blood transfusion, multiple sexual partner, previous abortion and reported cases of sexually transmitted infections.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the result and conclusion of this study, it was recommended that:

1. Government should make nationwide policy of routine and widespread HBV screening and prevention though vaccination among pregnant women in order to improve maternal and child health.
2. Pregnant women should attend health care service especially antenatal service to receive early diagnosis and immunization.
3. Women of childbearing age should avoid having more sexual partners as it may exposes them to several communicable disease such as hepatitis B infection.
4. Improving antenatal screening and providing targeted interventions in mothers could help eliminate HBV in the population.
5. Ministry of health should organize health education programs against unsafe abortion, multiple sexual partner and its consequences to community and to raise the awareness of mothers attending antenatal clinics.
6. Pregnant women should be screened for HBsAg at the first antenatal clinic visit for appropriate clinical management and effective prevention of vertical transmission.

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